

plexes calculated from the corrected magnetic susceptibilities determined at room temperature are given in Table 1. The small variation can be accounted for by assuming dimeric or chain polymeric structures in the solid state⁹. Molecular weight determinations in dioxan support dimeric structure.

The ir spectrum of the ligand has a band of medium intensity at $\sim 1690\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a strong band at 1620 cm^{-1} . The first band can be assigned to the asymmetric carbonyl stretch of the COOH group and is totally absent in the spectra of the complexes. This is replaced by a very strong band at 1600 cm^{-1} which is due to the coordinated carboxylate ion. Unfortunately, this then obscures the C=N band that is located at 1620 cm^{-1} in the free ligand. There is, however, no sign of a shoulder on the 1600 cm^{-1} band, and it can be assumed that because of coordination, the C=N stretch has been displaced to lower wavenumbers and is obscured by the more intense carboxylate band.

In the complexes, the presence of coordinated water is confirmed by the observation of a double hump around 3300 cm^{-1} due to ν_{OH} . The coordinated nature of the water molecule is further confirmed by the appearance of a rocking mode of medium intensity at 860 cm^{-1} . The strong band found around 1280 cm^{-1} in the ligand is assigned to phenolic C—O stretching vibration¹⁰. The shift towards higher frequency side indicates bonding of the phenolate oxygen. In the present complexes the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the carboxyl group occur at $1590\text{--}1600$ and $1440\text{--}1445\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively, with a difference $\Delta\nu_{\text{COO}}$ of $145\text{--}160\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Monodentate carboxylate group has a difference of $150\text{--}160\text{ cm}^{-1}$, but a bidentate or bridging carboxylate has a much closer difference ($< 120\text{ cm}^{-1}$)^{11,12}. Monodentate carboxylate groups are, therefore, indicated in the above chelates. The medium and somewhat broad intense band found in the region $460\text{--}480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ vibration. Medium intensity bands appearing at $350\text{--}370\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for these metal complexes are tentatively assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ vibration^{13,15}.

The observed mass loss agreed fairly well with the value calculated from pyrolytic experiments. In the present complexes, it was observed that the decomposition started only after 250° . So the water present was the coordinated water¹⁶. The initial decomposition temperature was frequently used to define the relative thermal stability of the metal complexes¹⁶. On the basis of the experimental findings, the relative thermal stability¹⁷ for the vanillideneanthranilic acid metal complexes can be given as $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} \approx \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Prof. C. P. Savariar, for facilities. The authors are thankful to U.G.C.,

New Delhi, for awarding a fellowship (to J.C.) and financial assistance (to G.P.).

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Complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Palladium(II), Zinc(II), Cadmium(II), Mercury(II) and Lead(II) with Glutathione

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Manuscript received 4 December 1984, revised 18 June 1986,
accepted 2 August 1986

RECENTLY, considerable interest has been shown in the binding of metal ions with amino acids and peptides as models for their interaction with proteins. Interaction of Zn^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} , Hg^{II} , Ag^{I} and Pd^{II} with glutathione (a tripeptide) was studied in solution by potentiometrically, spectrophotometrically and polarographically by various workers¹⁻⁹. These works prompted us to prepare Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Pb^{II} , Hg^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes with glutathione. The complexes were characterised by chemical analyses, magnetic moment data,

electronic and infrared spectra and thermogravimetric studies.

Experimental

Glutathione (reduced form) (Sigma) was used. Other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Preparation of metal-glutathione complexes: $MH(C_{10}H_{14}O_6N_3S)$, where $M=Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Pb^{II}, Hg^{II}$ and Pd^{II} ; and $MH(C_{10}H_{14}O_6N_3S) \cdot nH_2O$, where $M=Co^{II}, Ni^{II}$, and $n=2$. To glutathione (0.003 mol) dissolved in water (50 ml), $HgCl_2$ or $Pb(NO_3)_2$ or $ZnSO_4$ or $Cd(NO_3)_2$ (0.003 mol) in water (50 ml) was added and stirred for 0.5 h. The Hg^{II} complex was precipitated at pH 2, whereas Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} complexes were precipitated at pH 4, 6 and 3, respectively. The precipitates were filtered, washed with water and ethanol and finally dried in vacuum over fused $CaCl_2$. Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes were similarly prepared by treating the nitrate salts of these metals with glutathione at pH 7. pH in precipitation of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes were 6, 5 and 4, respectively.

Elemental analysis: Hg, Pb, Zn, Cd, Co, Ni and Pd content in the complexes were estimated following literature procedures¹⁰. Sulphur was estimated gravimetrically¹¹. Nitrogen was estimated microanalytically by Dumas method. The elemental analyses data are shown in the Table 1. Thermogravimetric data were recorded with a Simadzu DT-30 thermal analyser at the rate of 10° per min, and at room temperature 30 to 200° in the nitrogen atmosphere. The magnetic moments of the solid Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes were measured at room temperature in a Gouy balance using $CuSO_4 \cdot 4H_2O$ as the calibrant. The diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded with a Zeise PMQ II spectrophotometer with a reflectance attachment RA3 from the sample spread on filter paper in the range 200–1200 nm. The ir spectra were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer 599B spectrophotometer using KBr pellet from the range 4000–200 cm^{-1} .

Results and Discussion

The complexes of $Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Pb^{II}$ and Hg^{II} showed no loss of water on heating upto 140°. The loss at 160° for Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes corresponded to 2 moles of water per mole of the complexes.

The room temperature magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) values of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes were 4.38 and 3.14 B.M., respectively, which corresponded to their octahedral geometry^{12,13}. Somewhat lower value than free octahedral (4.8–5.2 B.M.). Co^{II} complex indicates a spin-state equilibrium between $^4T_{1g}$ and 3E_g states¹². The Pd^{II} complex was diamagnetic suggesting a square-planar geometry.

Electronic spectra: Diffuse reflectance spectra of the Co^{II} complex also points to an octahedral environment. The spectrum consisting of two principal bands at 9000 and 21200 cm^{-1} which could be assigned to the spin-allowed transitions, $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}(\nu_1)$ and $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P)(\nu_2)$, respectively¹⁴. A shoulder at 17500 cm^{-1} probably resulted from spin-forbidden transition¹⁵, $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}$. The reflectance spectra of the Ni^{II} complex showed two principal bands at 19500 and 18500 cm^{-1} which could be tentatively attributed to the spin-allowed transitions, $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{2g}(\nu_1)$ and $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(\nu_2)$, respectively, in an idealised octahedral symmetry¹⁶. The band at 27700 cm^{-1} was due to $^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(E)(\nu_3)$ transition. The dark yellow Pd^{II} compound showed two peaks at 37030 and 22220 cm^{-1} due to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1u}$ ¹⁷ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$ ¹⁷ transitions in a square-planar environment. The high intensity bands at about 35700 cm^{-1} in the spectra of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes were due to ligand only.

Ir spectra: The doublet peaks, appearing at 3350(s) and 3260(s) cm^{-1} in the ir spectra of glutathione, are due to symmetric stretching vibrations of $NHCO$ of the peptide group¹⁸. In the metal complexes, both the bands shifted to the higher frequency region 3600–3200 cm^{-1} . The

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF METAL—GLUTATHIONE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)			% Loss at 160° Found/ (Calcd.)
		M	N	S	
$ZnH(C_{10}H_{14}O_6N_3S)$	White	17.6 (17.7)	11.05 (11.30)	8.4 (8.6)	—
$CdH(C_{10}H_{14}O_6N_3S)$	White	26.5 (26.9)	9.80 (10.07)	7.5 (7.6)	—
$PbH(C_{10}H_{14}O_6N_3S)$	Pale yellow	40.7 (40.4)	8.06 (8.20)	6.1 (6.2)	—
$HgH(C_{10}H_{14}O_6N_3S)$	White	40.3 (39.5)	8.33 (8.30)	5.9 (6.3)	—
$CoH(C_{10}H_{14}O_6N_3S) \cdot 2H_2O$	Dark brown	14.4 (14.7)	10.57 (10.50)	8.3 (8.0)	8.9 (9.0)
$NiH(C_{10}H_{14}O_6N_3S) \cdot 2H_2O$	Brown	14.7 (14.5)	9.90 (10.50)	7.8 (8.0)	9.2 (9.0)
$PdH(C_{10}H_{14}O_6N_3S)$	Dark yellow	25.0 (25.8)	10.30 (10.20)	7.4 (7.7)	—

bands appearing at 1 660(w) and 1 560(m) cm^{-1} in the free ligand are one due to amide-I and the other amide-II bands¹⁸. In the complexes, these two bands are in the strong and broad bands covering the region 1 680–1 550 cm^{-1} . The peak appearing at 3 130–2 900 cm^{-1} in the free ligand is due to the NH_3^+ stretching frequency which comes from the zwitterion $^-\text{OOC}-\text{C}-\text{NH}_3^+$ of the amino acid moiety¹⁹. This zwitterion form was also supported by the appearance of NH_3^+ symmetric and asymmetric deformation vibration at 1 530 and 1 620 cm^{-1} , respectively. There was no band due to free NH_3 group in the ligands. But in the complexes the bands corresponding to NH_3 disappeared and bands around 3 300, 1 600(bs) and 1 300 cm^{-1} corresponding to the stretching, bending and wagging mode of vibrations of the coordinated NH_3 group²⁰ were observed. Thus the zwitterion moiety in the free ligand changed to NH_3 in the complexes. The strong band at 1 720(s) cm^{-1} in the free ligand was due to asymmetric vibration of COOH (non-amino acid)²⁰ and the band at 1 600(s) cm^{-1} is due to asymmetric stretching of COO^- group in amino acid part²². In the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes, there was no band at 1 720 cm^{-1} , instead strong and broad bands around 1 600 cm^{-1} were observed. This indicates that coordination occurred between the two acid groups through the deprotonation of COOH group of the non-amino acids part, the $-\text{COO}^-$ group of the amino acid part remaining unbonded. The ν_{SH} band at 2 500 cm^{-1} in glutathione disappeared on complexation. This indicated the linking of metal to sulphur (thiol) in all these complexes. The $\text{C}-\text{S}$ stretching frequency appeared in the 690–610 cm^{-1} region^{23,24} in the spectrum of glutathione. In the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes, there was an additional band due to the coordinated water²¹ observed at 960 cm^{-1} which was absent in the ir spectra of complexes of other metals and also in the free ligand.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. M. Choudhury and Dr. N. Roy Choudhury, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta-700 032, for their kind help.

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Stepwise Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Functions of the Chelates of L-Lysine Monohydrochloride with Iron(II), Strontium(II) and Antimony(III)

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Manuscript received 24 April 1985, revised 10 April 1986,
accepted 23 August 1986

COMPLEXATION behaviour of L-lysine has been extensively studied¹⁻⁵. A perusal of literature has revealed that no work has been reported on the metal chelates of L-lysine monohydrochloride. However, Jain *et al.*^{6,7} have reported the studies of some new metal chelates with L-lysine monohydrochloride.

The present work describes the thermodynamic functions of Fe^{II} , Sr^{II} and Sb^{III} with L-lysine monohydrochloride.

Experimental

All chemicals were of B.D.H. quality. Solutions of L-lysine monohydrochloride and metal nitrate/chloride were prepared in double-distilled water. The pH-metric investigations were carried out in aqueous media in the temperature range $15-30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ using carbonate-free 1 M NaOH. A constant ionic strength of 1 M was maintained by adding an appropriate quantity of potassium nitrate/chloride solu-